

Pulsed Light Decontamination and Modeling of *Salmonella* Reduction on Pecan Halves

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ABSTRACT

Pasteurization has been the traditional method of sterilizing tree nuts. Pulsed light (PL) has proven to be an inexpensive, efficient, and environmentally friendly non-thermal processing method for several foods. However, this technology has not been extensively explored with tree nuts. In this study, the efficacy of PL in inactivating *Salmonella* Typhimurium (ATCC 14028) on pecan halves was investigated. A Z-1000 sterilizing system was used to treat pecan samples at distance of 7, 11, and 15 cm from the quartz window in the PL chamber for 1, 5, 10, and 15 seconds. Each treatment included three pecan halves placed simultaneously in the sterilization chamber. Experiments were repeated three times for each treatment time and distance and then analyzed using the General Linear Models (GLM) procedure of SAS. The PL delivered to the surface of pecan halves achieved a maximum reduction of $1.69 \log_{10}$ CFU/g for treatment time of 15 seconds at a distance of 7 cm. The treatment with the highest log reduction was chosen to determine the pecan halves' quality characteristics. A significant reduction in moisture content in pecan samples was observed immediately after treatment, however, after storing at 4°C for 24 hours, no difference in moisture content was observed between treated and untreated samples. Changes in color (a^* and b^* values) were observed in treated pecan samples immediately after treatment (0 hours), but they regained their color after 24 hours. The total color difference between untreated and treated pecan samples was not significant, indicating that the treatment did not adversely affect the overall appearance of the pecan halves. Similarly, there were no differences in hardness values between treated and untreated pecan halves. This study demonstrates that PL can be used as an effective sterilizing method for *Salmonella*. Artificial neural network (ANN) prediction models were developed to predict the PL *Salmonella* inactivation on pecan halves as a function of distance and treatment time using the Backpropagation (ANN-BP) and Kalman Filter (ANN-KL) learning algorithm. Their performance was compared with that of regression models. Various statistical indices, including R^2 between actual and predicted outputs, were evaluated to select the best models. Prediction plots for log reduction values indicated that the ANN-BP and ANN-KF models demonstrated robust accuracy, with R values of 0.78 ± 0.39 and 0.80 ± 0.39 , respectively, in predictions from new unseen patterns, compared to the performance of the regression models ($R = 0.60 \pm 0.37$). The results indicated that PL could be used as a potential decontamination method for pecan halves, and ANN models could provide reliable prediction of the *Salmonella* population.

Keywords: Artificial Neural Network; Bacteria; Contamination; Prediction; Non-thermal Processing.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Pecan trees (*Carya illinoensis*) are native to America and can be found in Northern Mexico as well as the Southern United States (U.S.). In the U.S., pecan farming began in the 1800s, and Georgia accounts for 33% of the total crop in the country (≈ 45 million kg, in-shell, McDaniel and Jadeja, 2021). The demand for nuts and their products has been increasing every year as customers' interest in nutrition and health has grown (Gervasi *et al.*, 2021). Pecans provide many nutritional benefits to consumers, as they are rich in several nutrients and possess antioxidants, anti-cancerous, and other disease-preventing properties, and thus are recognized as one of the nutrient foods for human health (Atanasov *et al.*, 2018).

Tree nuts, despite being a low moisture food, have been frequently associated with several outbreaks and recalls due to contamination with bacteria, such as *E. coli* O157: H7, *Salmonella*, and *Listeria monocytogenes* (Zhang *et al.*, 2017; Gyawali *et al.*, 2024). *Salmonella* can survive on the shucks and in low-moisture food products kept at refrigerated or room temperature for several weeks to months. During rainfall, pathogens present on outer shells can cross-contaminate nearby in-shell pecans. According to Brar *et al.* (2016), 0.95% of in-shell pecans were tested positive for prevalence of *Salmonella* when studied over four harvest seasons. *Salmonella* can also survive up to a year on pecan kernels when stored under ambient, refrigerated, and frozen conditions (Brar *et al.*, 2015). Although there have been no outbreaks associated with pecans and its products yet, a few recalls due to potential *Salmonella* contamination have been reported (Yemmireddy *et al.*, 2020). Hence, enhancing the safety of pecans against *Salmonella* contamination is to be considered.

Traditional methods of tree nut disinfection involve steam pasteurization, drying, sterilization, or chemical means, such as roasting and

blanching. Even though these techniques have long been used for microbial inactivation, they also degrade certain nutrients and can affect nut quality (Bhavaya and Hebbar, 2017; Allai *et al.*, 2023). Therefore, it is important to find other effective and safe alternatives, including non-thermal techniques, to these existing methods. Pulsed light (PL) is one such emerging non-thermal processing technology, which has the potential to decontaminate food products, including tree nuts. The PL can rapidly inactivate microorganisms, such as *Salmonella* and *E. coli*, in very short treatment times (Oms-Oliu *et al.*, 2000). The U.S Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has approved the use of PL treatment of food (Federal Register, 1996). The light generated by pulsed UV lamps consists of a continuum of energy from UV to infrared that pulses several times, and each pulse lasts between 2 and 100 ms. The PL has a modest energy input, which can yield high peak power dissipation and has a germicidal effect (Demirci and Panico, 2008). Pulsed light has an advantage over other thermal processing methods and is considered environmentally friendly, as there is no need for any chemicals, water, and leaves no residual compounds (Gómez-López *et al.*, 2007). Although several studies have been conducted to determine the effect of PL on inactivating microorganisms in food products (Ozer and Demirci, 2006), its use in tree nut processing is limited. One such study is the evaluation by Izmirliglu *et al.* (2020) on walnut halves inoculated with *Salmonella enteritidis*. A maximum log reduction of 3.18 CFU/g was obtained after PL treatment at 8 cm for 45 s. Despite its potential antimicrobial efficacy, there are some limitations with this technology: Longer duration of PL for food processing can cause the temperatures of food products to rise that could affect the food quality. The possibility of shadowing is another disadvantage of PL, which interferes with absorption of UV rays by microorganisms and ultimately affects the inactivation rate. In addition, PL has a more

limited penetration capacity in opaque, rough, and irregular surfaces than in smooth and transparent food materials (Bhavya and Hebbar, 2017).

Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) are nonlinear computational modeling techniques inspired by biological neural networks (Basheer and Hajmeer, 2000), while other modeling techniques, such as statistical regression, predict linear patterns from data. The development of ANN models involves training, testing, and validation. Hence, the pool of available records is divided into these three datasets in such a way that the records in each dataset are independent of each other. The networks are trained with various algorithms, such as Backpropagation and Kalman filter. The goal of these algorithms is to reduce the amount of error between the predicted output and the measured output (Gosukonda *et al.*, 2015). The objective of using ANN models was to develop predictive models for quantifying the PL decontamination of *Salmonella* on pecan halves and to compare their performance with that of statistical models, assessing their suitability as a tool for online processing in the food industry. Modeling techniques that achieve optimal prediction accuracy for *Salmonella* inactivation on pecans would not only enhance product quality and public perception from a safety standpoint but also improve the marketability of pecan products. Furthermore, this information is invaluable for optimizing storage and handling conditions, enabling practices that maintain the highest pecan quality. Hence, the objective of this study was to evaluate the efficacy of PL decontamination on the survival of *Salmonella* on pecan halves and to predict the PL inactivation potential using ANN models.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Bacterial Strain, Sample Preparation and Inoculation

Salmonella enterica subsp. *enterica* serovar Typhimurium (ATCC 14028) was used in this study. The KWIK-STIK pouch was allowed to equilibrate at room temperature and the inoculum

was prepared as per the manufacturer's instructions. Georgia mammoth pecan halves were obtained from Lane Southern Orchards (Fort Valley, GA, USA). Forty μL of *Salmonella* (≈ 7.0 log) was inoculated at four randomly chosen spots on pecan halves (≈ 2 g) surface in a hood (Labconco Purified Class II Biosafety Cabinet, Labconco Corp., Kansas, MO, USA). Inoculated pecans were air dried in the hood for 30 min for bacterial attachment.

2.2. Pulsed Light Treatment

A Z-1000 Modular Sterilization System (XENON Corporation, Wilmington, MA, USA) was used in this study. Inoculated pecan samples were treated with PL for 1, 5, 10 and 15 s at 7, 11 and 15 cm from the light source. Inoculated pecan samples that were not treated were used as controls. Pulsed light treatment radiant energy was $1.27 \text{ J}/\text{cm}^2$ per pulse.

2.3. Microbiological Analysis

Treated and untreated samples were placed individually in a stomacher bag with 10 mL of 0.1% peptone water and homogenized with a stomacher (Model 400 stomacher, Seaward, UK Brinkmann Instrument INC., West Bury, NY, USA) for 2 min at 230 RPM. The samples were then serially diluted with 0.1% sterile peptone water and the appropriate dilutions were spiral plated on to tryptic soy agar using an Eddy Jet 2 Spiral plater (Neutec Group, Farmingdale, NY, USA). Colonies were counted after incubating (Sheldon Manufacturing, Inc Cornelius, OR, USA) for 18-20 h at 37°C using a Bantex colony counter (Model 920A, America Bantex Corp., Chandler, AZ, USA).

2.4. Quality Analysis

For quality analysis, PL treated samples (7 cm and 15 s) that had the maximum log reduction were chosen.

2.4.1. Moisture content

Moisture content of treated and untreated pecan halves at 0 and 24 h of storage was measured by placing the samples in an oven at 105°C for 24 h.

2.4.2. Color analysis

The total color difference (ΔE) of treated and untreated pecan samples at 0 and 24 h of storage after PL treatment was measured using a ColorFlex EZ colorimeter (HunterLab, Reston, VA, USA). Pecan samples were kept on the port at three different 90° surface positions to measure the color (L^* lightness, a^* redness, and b^* yellowness) values, and the ΔE was calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{Total color difference } (\Delta E) = [(\Delta L^*)^2 + (\Delta a^*)^2 + (\Delta b^*)^2]^{0.5} \quad \dots (1)$$

2.4.3. Texture analysis

Hardness of the samples was determined using a CTX Texture Analyzer (Brookfield AmeTek, Middleboro, MA, USA). Hardness of each pecan was determined using the following parameters: Trigger force: 15.0 g, Deformation: 20 mm, and Test Speed: 4 mm/s and measured by placing the sample in triangular slit of a shear blade.

2.5. Statistical Analysis

The experiment was conducted using a completely randomized design with 3x4 factorial treatment arrangement. Factor one was the distance from the light source, with three levels, and factor two was the treatment time, with four levels. Data were analyzed using ANOVA, and means were compared using Tukey-Kramer Test using SAS (version 9.4, SAS Institute, Cary, NC, USA). The number of samples for each treatment was three, plated in duplicates, and the experiments were repeated three times on different days.

Multiple linear regression models were developed using PROC REG (Regression Procedure) and GLM (General Linear Models) procedures of the SAS® system (Version 9.4, SAS Institute) for the prediction of log reductions of *Salmonella* as a function of treatment time and distance from the light source, as described by the equation:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 \quad \dots (2)$$

Where, Y is the log reduction of *Salmonella*; β_0 is Y – intercept; β_n is model coefficients; X_1 is distance (7, 11, and 15 cm) and X_2 is treatment time (1, 5, 10, and 15 s).

2.6. ANN Modeling

Artificial neural network models were developed using NeuralWorks Predict® and NeuralSight software to predict the inactivation of *Salmonella* (\log_{10} CFU/g) on pecan halves treated with PL as a function of time and distance from the light source. Artificial neural networks were chosen for their ability to model complex relationships without requiring data preprocessing (NeuralWorks Predict, 2018). Experimental data from the PL inactivation study were used to train the models, with treatment time and distance as inputs, and predicted *Salmonella* reduction on the pecan surface as the output.

A multilayer perceptron (MLP) neural network with a feedforward architecture (Fig. 1) was chosen for its ability to learn complex relationships in nonlinear data (Zou *et al.*, 2008). Multilayer perceptron has universal approximation capabilities and provides compact representations, making them suitable for our study (Abiodun *et al.*, 2018). In an MLP, the input layer receives data, the hidden layer performs computations using transfer functions, and the output layer makes predictions (Zou *et al.*, 2008; Abiodun *et al.*, 2018). The software builds the network incrementally, adding hidden units one by one and connecting them to previous units. This step-by-step construction process is called “cascade learning” (Gosukonda *et al.*, 2015), where each unit aims to maximize its correlation with the desired output. The “cascade” refers to the stepwise construction, and “correlation” refers to how the units learn by maximizing their output's correlation with the desired outcome (Fahlman and Lebiere, 1990).

Fig. 1. A schematic diagram of MLP neural network model

This study used two learning rules: Backpropagation (ANN-BP) and the Kalman filter (ANN-KF) (Luttmann and Mercorelli, 2021) to improve prediction accuracy and data fit in ANN models. Backpropagation uses gradient descent (Rumelhart *et al.*, 1986) and Gauss-Newton methods (Osborne, 1992) to refine predictions, while KF estimates parameters through recursive prediction and update (Kalman, 1960), filtering out noise from uncertain observations (Puskorius and Feldkamp, 1991). Given the potential for noise in microbiological data, the KF's noise-filtering capabilities were particularly relevant.

2.6.1. Data records for model training, testing and validation

There were 144 out of 216 experimental measurements (inputs and outputs) used for training and internal testing, while the remaining 72 were reserved for independent validation to develop ANN predictive models. Data were assigned to each set to ensure independence, preventing model overfitting. The training was further split equally (72 each) by the software for training and internal testing. The training dataset adjusted the model's parameters, while the

internal test data evaluated its performance. Finally, the independent validation set confirmed the model's generalizability beyond the training and internal test data.

2.6.2. Selection of ANN models

Network configurations were optimized empirically, with performance comparisons based on statistical indices across training, testing, and validation datasets. These indices included Pearson correlation (R), standard deviation, various error measures (average absolute error, maximum absolute error, root mean square residual), and metrics like accuracy factor, mean absolute relative residual, bias factor, and mean relative percentage residual (data not shown). Ultimately, the best models were selected based on R values.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Efficacy of PL in Inactivating *Salmonella* on Pecan Halves

The initial population on the surface of pecan halves was $7.11 \log_{10}$ CFU/g (positive control). No natural microflora was found on the surface of samples that were not inoculated (negative control). The efficacy of PL on the surface of

pecan halves at 7, 11, and 15 cm is presented in Fig. 2. The maximum reduction of 1.69 log₁₀ CFU/g was achieved when treated at 7 cm for 15 s. Increasing treatment time (1 s to 5 s) showed no significant increase in log reductions, however 5 s to 15 s showed significant ($P \leq 0.05$) increase in log reductions at all distances (7, 11, and 15 cm).

The effect of distance on the reductions was significantly observed from 5 s to 15 s treatments. The longer treatment times might have resulted in better penetration of PL through the grooves on the pecan surface, overcoming the shadowing effect, and resulting in higher *Salmonella* reduction on pecan halves.

Fig. 2. Inactivation of *Salmonella* on pecan halves using PL at 7, 11, and 15 cm from the light source (n = 18)

Overall, treatment time and distance from the light source had significant ($p < 0.0001$) effects on the inactivation efficacy of PL against *Salmonella*. A significant ($p < 0.0001$) interaction was also found between treatment time and distance. The results obtained in this study are consistent with results of another study that reported a maximum reduction of 3.18 log₁₀ CFU/g on shelled walnuts after PL treatment at 8 cm for 45 s, however, there was less than one log reduction for 1-15 s and showed no significant difference in log reductions for 20 to 40 s (Izmirlioglu *et al.*, 2020). The reduction achieved in walnuts after 15 s treatment was 1.88 log CFU/g, consistent with our study, and the minor difference in the reduction achieved might be due to difference in the energy generated per pulse and surface morphological differences between the nuts.

3.2. Effect of PL on Pecan Quality

3.2.1. Moisture content

Moisture content is an important quality parameter that affects the shelf life of pecans. Table 1 shows the moisture content of treated pecans at 7 cm for 15 s at 0 and 24 h of storage at refrigerated temperature. At 0 h, PL reduced the moisture level of pecans from 3.9% to 2.2%, possibly due to the heat generated by the PL. However, after storing at 4°C for 24 h, no difference in moisture content was observed between the samples.

3.2.2. Texture analysis

Texture is one of the important indicators for assessing pecan quality and is measured by evaluating hardness, which is the peak force (N) required to deform a food material. The differences in hardness value of control (38.17 N)

and treated pecans (37.76 N) at 0 h were statistically different compared to the control (36.18 N). After 24 h of storage, there was a slight decrease in the hardness value of treated (36.07 N) samples, but it was not effect on the textural quality of pecans.

Table 1. Moisture content and hardness of PL treated pecan halves (Mean ± SD; n = 12).

Sample type	Moisture content, % (w.b.)*		Hardness value, N	
	Storage period			
	0 h	24 h	0 h	24 h
Untreated	3.90 ± 3.91 ^a	3.69 ± 1.12 ^a	38.17 ± 6.90 ^{NS}	36.18 ± 6.25 ^{NS}
Treated	2.20 ± 0.61 ^b	3.2 ± 0.33 ^a	37.76 ± 4.80 ^{NS}	36.07 ± 6.06 ^{NS}

*Mean values within the same column followed by different letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$); ^{NS} Non-significant.

3.2.3. Color analysis

Table 2 shows the color of treated (7 cm, 15 s) and untreated pecans at 0 and 24 h of storage. At 0 h, untreated and treated samples showed no differences in L^* values. There was a slight

change in a^* and b^* values for treated samples after 24 h storage at 4°C, however, the total color difference between treated and untreated samples, was below 3.0, which falls within the acceptable range, where the difference is noticeable but not significant (Arthur *et al.*, 2025).

Table 2. L^* , a^* , and b^* values and total color difference, ΔE of PL treated pecan halves (Mean ± SD; n = 12).

Sample type	Color values							
	Storage period of 0 h				Storage period of 24 h			
	L^*	a^*	b^*	ΔE	L^*	a^*	b^*	ΔE
Untreated	43.9±1.7 ^a	14.6±0.5 ^a	29.2±1.9 ^a	-	43.9±1.7 ^a	14.6±0.5 ^a	29.2±1.9 ^a	-
Treated	43.18±2.1 ^a	13.7±0.6 ^b	26.9±2.2 ^b	3.3 ± 1.2	43.9±2. ^a	14.3±0.7 ^a	28.8±0.9 ^a	2.9±1.2

Mean values within the same column followed by different letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$).

3.3. ANN Modeling

3.3.1. Prediction performance of regression and ANN models

The data used in this study were obtained from experiments that measured *Salmonella* reduction (output) on pecan halves as a function of distance

from the light source and treatment time with PL (inputs). The final regression model was selected based upon its relatively lower standard deviations and a higher regression coefficient (Eq. 3):

$$SR = 0.925 + (0.014 t) - (0.045 d) \quad \dots (3)$$

($R = 0.60 \pm 0.37$)

Where, SR is *Salmonella* reduction, \log_{10} CFU/g; t is treatment time, s and d is distance from the light source, cm.

Table 3 shows the comparison of the performance of regression and ANN models in predicting *Salmonella* reduction on pecan surfaces based on treatment time and distance. While regression models had a lower Pearson correlation ($R = 0.60 \pm 0.37$) for validation data, both ANN models (BP: $R = 0.73 \pm 0.31$, KF: $R = 0.73 \pm 0.36$) achieved slightly higher R values. However, these higher values in validation compared to training data (BP: $R = 0.81 \pm 0.41$, KF: $R = 0.84 \pm 0.41$) suggest

potential overfitting, where the models memorized noise instead of learning general patterns. This might be due to the models having low bias but high variance, meaning they fit the training data too closely at the expense of generalizability (Jeyamkondan *et al.*, 2001). The limitations of the model include the assumption of linear relationships, exclusion of other relevant factors, such as temperature, pecan surface characteristics, or the initial level of contamination, and the potential for reduced accuracy under different conditions. These limitations should be considered when applying the model to real-world situations.

Table 3. Pearson's correlations ($R \pm SD$) between predicted and experimental values of regression and neural networks models.

Output	Regression model	ANN-Back propagation		ANN-Kalman filter	
	All values	Training*	Validation	Training*	Validation
	R	R	R	R	R
Log reduction on pecan halves	0.60 ± 0.37	0.81 ± 0.41	0.73 ± 0.31	0.84 ± 0.41	0.73 ± 0.36

* The $R \pm SD$ values of training and test data sets were pooled and shown as training.

Prediction plots of ANN-BP and ANN-KF (validation data) and regression models in Table 4 reveal a clear difference in their performance. Both ANN-BP and ANN-KF models closely aligned with the measured values across treatment levels, while the regression model failed to capture the observed trends. Table 4 further confirms the experimental observation of increasing *Salmonella* reduction with PL exposure time up to 15 s and distances of 7 and 11 cm. However, a decrease in reduction in log reduction occurred at 15 cm at all treatment times of PL. The regression model missed this crucial pattern.

While predictions on mid-range treatment seemed to be more accurate for both ANN models, ANN models often exhibit varying performance across different output variables (Dong and Zhao, 2014). The results demonstrate the superior prediction ability of ANN models compared to the regression model, especially for unseen patterns, despite lower R values on validation data compared to training. Generally, the main advantage of neural network models over regression models is the ability to recognize the relationship between input and output datasets without specifying a prior relationship.

Table 4. Comparison of models against measured data, presenting the average predicted log reduction (CFU/g) values for each treatment (n = 18).

Treatments		Models			
Distance, cm	Time, s	Measured	Backpropagation	Kalman Filter	Regression
7	1	0.57	0.39	0.28	0.52
7	5	0.27	0.27	0.31	0.68
7	10	0.77	0.95	0.89	0.89
7	15	1.37	1.26	1.33	1.09
11	1	0.75	0.37	0.38	0.32
11	5	0.22	0.25	0.25	0.48
11	10	0.77	0.95	0.89	0.89
11	15	1.28	1.26	1.33	1.09
15	1	0.37	0.47	0.50	0.12
15	5	0.29	0.20	0.18	0.28
15	10	0.38	0.40	0.38	0.49
15	15	0.58	0.41	0.42	0.69

4. CONCLUSIONS

The application of PL treatment has demonstrated significant potential in enhancing the safety and maintaining quality of pecans. Log reductions of 0.36, 0.30, 0.87, and 1.69 CFU/g were achieved for treatment times of 1, 5, 10, and 15 s, respectively, at 7 cm distance. A significant reduction in moisture content in pecan samples was observed immediately after treatment. However, after storing at 4°C for 24 h, no difference in moisture content was observed between treated and untreated samples. Changes in color (a^* and b^* values) were observed in treated pecan samples immediately after treatment (0 h), but they regained their color after 24 h storage. The total color difference (ΔE) between

untreated and treated pecan samples was not significant, indicating that the treatment did not adversely affect the overall appearance of the pecan halves. Similarly, there were no differences in hardness values between treated and untreated pecan halves. Thus, this study showed that PL treatment can effectively inactivate *Salmonella* on pecan halves without compromising their quality. The regression model failed to capture important trends observed in the experimental data. The ANN models exhibited higher correlation coefficients compared to the regression model and provided more accurate predictions of *Salmonella* reduction on pecan halves. The ANN models not only exhibited the optimal prediction accuracy for *Salmonella* inactivation on pecans, but would also

enhance product quality and public perception from a safety standpoint and improve the marketability of pecan products. This study demonstrated that PL has the potential to be considered as a novel decontamination method for pecan halves and other tree nuts. Further research is needed to optimize its use for commercial applications in various tree nuts.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION

Kumudini Talari (Investigation, Methodology), Hema Degala (Investigation, Methodology, Writing-original draft), Ajit Mahapatra (Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Supervision), Rabin Gyawali (Methodology, Writing-original draft), Ramana Gosukonda (Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing-original draft), Thomas Terrill (Methodology, Editing-original draft)

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